

SPEECH DEVELOPMENT: REASONING OF PRESCHOOLERS IN A MODERN KINDERGARTEN

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the problem of speech development — the reasoning of older preschoolers, the use of modern multimedia equipment in educational activities — the digital laboratory "Naurasha in the country of Naurandia".

Keywords: speech-reasoning, speech development at preschool age, formation of skills, digital laboratory.

INTRODUCTION

Mastering the native language is one of the important acquisitions of a child in preschool childhood. It is acquisitions, since speech is not given to a person from birth. It should take time for the child to start talking. And adults should make a lot of efforts to ensure that the child's speech develops correctly and in a timely manner. In modern preschool education, speech is considered as one of the foundations of the upbringing and education of children, since the success of teaching children at school, the ability to communicate with people and general intellectual development depends on the level of mastery of coherent speech. By coherent speech we mean a semantic expanded statement that provides communication and mutual understanding.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

One of the most difficult types of coherent speech, the development of which is engaged in kindergarten, is speech-reasoning. Reasoning requires the speaker to have sufficiently developed independent thinking and proficiency in appropriate language means. Reasoning is a model of a monological message with a generalized causal meaning based on a complete or abbreviated conclusion. The reasoning is conducted in order to reach a conclusion. The reasoning contains an explanation of a fact, a certain point of view is argued, revealing cause-and-effect relationships and relationships. The basis for reasoning is accumulated knowledge, the content and level of which affect the depth of reasoning, i.e. cognitive activity must reach a certain level. The main thing in reasoning, according to O. A. Nechaeva, is the identification of cause-and-effect relationships, the argumentation of something. The establishment of cause-and-effect relationships in reasoning involves the use of complex constructions, a clearer logic of utterance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An important role in reasoning is played by mental operations — analysis, synthesis, generalizations, comparisons, abstraction, concretization.

- formation of the ability to establish causal relationships and dependencies in objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality and express them in speech; - formation of children's ideas about the essence of speech – reasoning, about the function of this type of speech;

- training in the ability to identify essential signs of phenomena to prove the thesis put forward;
- formation of ideas about the design of the text – reasoning in speech, about the linguistic features of the explanation (thesis, proof, conclusion, the words "because", "since", "therefore", "that's why" are used between the parts, etc.);
- training in the use of introductory modal words in the proof: firstly, secondly, thirdly, for greater clarity of argumentation. For the persuasiveness of the explanation, the use of examples;
- encouragement of an active search for language means corresponding to the proof that most adequately convey the thought-proof.

But it is necessary to understand that the formation of the prerequisites for coherent evidence-based speech occurs in observations of the surrounding world, living and inanimate nature. The educator should give some knowledge about the observed and activate them with the help of a problematic question. The formation of children's reasoning depends on how complete the children's knowledge of the subject about which they are reasoning. The richer the life experience, the more capable the child is to reason. The understanding of cause-and-effect relationships is most fully realized with direct actions with objects. Therefore, children's experimentation has an important place in this issue. Any experiment allows children to visually trace dependencies of various kinds, establish logical connections, identify essential features, properties of objects and phenomena to prove the theses put forward, teaches them to draw conclusions. The work on the development of speech-reasoning of older preschoolers is organized quite effectively with the help of a modern educational tool — the digital laboratory "Naurasha in the country of Naurandia". This children's digital laboratory, consisting of 8 modules, each of which is dedicated to a separate topic:

- "Temperature"
- "Light"
- "Sound"
- "Magnetic field"
- "Electricity"
- "Force"
- "Pulse"
- "Acidity".

Each module includes a digital sensor in the form of a "Ladybug" and the necessary equipment. The laboratory contains a methodological guide for the teacher, as well as software. The effectiveness of the formation of speech — reasoning in preschoolers depends on how clear, close and interesting the proposed task is for them. And the topics for reasoning that we offer to our students really interest the guys.

- "Why do I need to know the temperature of the water?",
- "Why does a person need ice?",
- "My favorite time of the year",
- "Why do I need different sounds?",
- "Why do I need quiet and loud, high and low sounds?",
- "What would happen if would we not have heard sounds?",
- "Why is there no sound in space?"

The work is carried out through the organization of club activities. The kindergarten has a children's club "Reasoning with Naurasha", where children are engaged not only in experimentation, but also have the opportunity to discuss, make assumptions, voice their own evidence, formulate conclusions. Since the digital laboratory is installed in the office of developmental learning, the children's club is located there. With a certain frequency, namely, — 1 time a month, older preschoolers visit it. Here they have the opportunity to reflect, discuss and answer any question. Club members (children) solve the questions received by the club from parents, younger comrades, fairy-tale heroes and other characters. They are assisted in this by the interactive host of the Naurash laboratory. This is an animated character, a little scientist, an assistant to teachers and a friend of children who shares knowledge on a given topic and advises children to conduct this or that experience.

Of course, the work on the development of speech reasoning proceeds under the guidance of an adult. And the effectiveness of pedagogical influence depends on the activity of the child in the conditions of speech activity. Therefore, the children first try to answer the question that entered the club on their own. Then they turn to Naurasha for confirmation of their answers or for practical help. In any case, Naurasha will offer to conduct an experiment, and will advise how best to conduct the experiment. Next, the children conduct an experiment during which Naurasha reacts vividly to the actions of small experimenters, making witty remarks and comments. Experience helps children find the right answer to a question. But our main task is to help the child formulate it. After the logical connections are established by the children, the essential features, properties of an object or phenomenon are highlighted, the teacher's work with the children will follow on the compilation of the reasoning text according to the classical methodology. The work continues in groups where the corners of "Naurashi" are located — after all, speech development occurs not only during direct educational activities, but also in the free and joint activities of children and adults, in the process of situations that have arisen, communication, dialogues, games. That's why "Naurashi" corners are organized in groups of senior preschool age. In these corners there are illustrations with problematic plots, riddles, questions, books, algorithms, schemes, models of reasoning construction.

CONCLUSION

Relying on such models helps children to build a statement, to control the construction of evidence. We noticed that the more active a child is, the more he is involved in experimental activities, the better his speech result. Thus, under favorable conditions, the child is able to use rather complex forms of reasoning. Gradually, the older preschooler develops the ability to think independently, to coordinate their judgments with each other and with reality, not to fall into contradictions. Working on the development of speech in kindergarten, it is necessary to immerse the child in an environment that stimulates his speech activity. In the arsenal of a teacher there should be tools that will help to work on the development of speech in different types of activities, allowing you to develop the most important qualities associated with preparing for school, such as creativity, arbitrariness, initiative, independence, curiosity. Digital laboratory "Naurasha" is a modern and effective means of speech development that meets the needs of preschool teachers.

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